

THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING A READING CULTURE OF STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15719438>

Abstract. *Today, in an era of rapid development of information technologies, the issue of forming and developing a reading culture of students remains one of the important and urgent tasks of the education system. Therefore, this article focuses on the issues of improving the methodology for forming a reading culture. Also, the state of reading culture, which is of incomparable importance in the ideological and ideological development of students and youth in our society, the opinions of some scientists on this issue and socio-pedagogical mechanisms aimed at increasing the reading culture of students are considered.*

Keywords: *Adolescent generation, students, books, reading culture, knowledge, spiritual heritage, needs, reading, analysis of works of art, literacy, methodological approaches.*

The educational value of books in raising a well-rounded generation is incomparable. Our wise people say that books are treasures. And the knowledge gained from them is wealth. The worldview of every student who reads a book develops, and the possibilities of understanding material existence expands. It is not for nothing that our wise people say, "If you don't have a good interlocutor, read a book." If the habit of reading is formed in young people, the book itself will teach them all the remaining actions on the path to perfection. That is why the book is one of the greatest miracles created by the human mind. Therefore, it is reading that gives a person knowledge and information, enriches his spiritual world.

Great attention is paid in Uzbekistan to the issue of the moral development of young people, their upbringing in the spirit of humanity. The strategic tasks of developing our country and strengthening its independence proposed by our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev include the training of a spiritually mature, harmonious generation and competitive personnel, as well as the upbringing of young people with a strong sense of national pride who can help society in solving social problems. [1] In implementing these tasks, "we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors" [2] and the upbringing of the growing younger generation in the spirit of universal human values built on the basis of Eastern education imposes a huge responsibility on society.

Of course, the role of education in solving these tasks is incomparable. In this regard, the Head of our state emphasizes the issue of forming a reading culture in students, which is one of the national characteristics. Ozod Sharafiddinov, a prominent literary scholar and translator, who is honored as a person of spiritual courage, describes the seven wonders of the world and says, "The seven wonders are a fiery hymn to the human mind, thought, and soul, an eternal monument to the greatness of human genius. However, despite this, there is another miracle in the world, the greatness and holiness of which are no less than the combined greatness and beauty of the seven wonders. This miracle is a book. Many great people have noted that a book is a miracle, even if it is a miracle, it is the first miracle," he writes. For example, the writer and playwright C. Swayge writes, "Wherever there is a book, a person does not remain isolated from himself, within his own

scope, he becomes acquainted with all the world-famous achievements of the past and present, with the thoughts and feelings of all humanity.”

Writer and philosopher J. Swift said, “Books are the children of the mind,” educator and writer J. Comenius said, “Books are a tool for spreading wisdom,” and philosopher and historian F. Bacon wrote, “Books are ships of thought, sailing on the waves of time and carefully carrying their precious cargo from generation to generation.” Thus, great scholars, wise men, writers, and scientists likened the book to a miracle, a light, a pillar of thought, a symbol of eternity and spirituality, a source of knowledge, a faithful friend, and a mirror of the times. Most importantly, the book is an invincible force in the fight against ignorance with enlightenment. In recent years, the scope of work on promoting a reading culture among students and young people in our country has expanded and improved in quality. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PR-3271 dated September 13, 2017 “On the Program of Comprehensive Measures to Develop the System of Publishing and Distribution of Book Products, Increase and Promote the Culture of Book Reading and Reading”, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 781 dated December 14, 2020 on the National Program for the Development and Support of Reading Culture in 2020–2025, and a number of other documents serve as a roadmap for the development of the sector. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 781 dated December 14, 2020 provides for the implementation of the National Program for the Development and Support of Reading Culture in 2020–2025 in three stages. Stage I - implementation of measures to improve organizational and legal mechanisms for the development of a reading culture in 2020-2021; Stage II - strengthening the infrastructure for reading in 2022-2023; Stage III - intensively developing the reading culture of young people in 2024-2025, improving the quality of human capital through the growth of their intellectual potential.

Reading books is the food and product of human thought. Our esteemed President Sh. Mirziyoev also expressed his thoughts on this: “A person who reads books and works on himself will have wings. He will not be indifferent. He will have strength. Therefore, he will not offend anyone. He will not flatter adults, he has knowledge, he has knowledge. That is why we say read books. If you read books, you will know how to ask questions”. A person who reads books will never be humiliated anywhere. All the property and wealth of a person can be taken away, but no one can ever take away a person’s knowledge and wisdom. Knowledge is a permanent inheritance and wealth for a person.

The Fourth Initiative of the Decree “On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” on the development of reading is to raise the morale of young people and widely promote reading among them “as an important factor in ensuring the implementation of the tasks set by the program.” A book is a thankless teacher, and knowledge is an inexhaustible treasure. In this regard, we considered it appropriate to dwell on the opinions of some of the following scholars on the methodology for developing a reading culture in students. In particular, Safo Matchon: “Reading is not determined by the number of books read, but rather by reading with understanding, that is, by reading with purpose. Based on this, we can say that the level of reading culture and talent is determined by how well the reader understands the idea that the writer wants to convey, that is, by understanding the “language” of the work. Therefore, our literature always needs talented readers along with talented writers.” In his opinion, the talent for reading is not innate, but is developed through upbringing.

When it comes to reading, it is worth citing the following opinion of the German thinker Goethe: “People do not imagine how much time is spent on learning to read, I have devoted 80 years of my life to this, but I still cannot say that I have learned it.” Professor V.F. Asmus, in his article “Reading - Labor and Creativity” defines reading as follows: “During reading, the work is not poured into the reader’s brain like water poured from one jug to another, but is re-perceived by the creative reader”. “In developed foreign countries” writes H. Tokhtaboev, “reading has been elevated to the level of a science. Reading is not only about promoting books, but also about teaching how to read books, how to choose a book to read, how to understand the essence, that is, how to understand oneself with the help of books”.

According to his pedagogical approach, V.V. Davydov emphasizes active learning in education and emphasizes the need to develop a reading culture not only through passive reading, but also through active, problem-solving situations. In his opinion, it is important to teach students to express their thoughts, analyze the text, and apply what they have read in practice. According to L.V. Zankov’s theory of educational effectiveness, he suggests encouraging students to read by stimulating a high level of activity in education. In forming a reading culture, in his opinion, attention is paid to the need to develop students’ independent work skills in the educational process. According to the critical thinking approach of the American scientist John Dewey, he advocates building education on the basis of problem solving and critical thinking. He emphasizes the need to develop students not only as receivers of information, but also as analyzers, questioners, and exchangers of ideas in the process of reading books. R.M. Gilyazov emphasizes that the culture of reading is an important factor in the spiritual and moral development of a person. According to him, the methodology must include the selection of books based on topics and genres that interest each student and encourage them to read. An individualized approach emphasizes that reading books is more effective.

P.V. Simonenko, speaking about the role of the communication process in education, suggests involving students in a group exchange of ideas about the text read. He estimates that such an interactive approach to developing a culture of reading creates a reader-writer-communication system and develops critical thinking and creative thinking.

Uzbek scientists, for example, A. Ergashev and Z. Islamova, consider modern digital technologies to be an effective tool in developing a culture of reading. They believe that the use of electronic books, online libraries and interactive textbooks will interest students in reading, and at the same time increase their independent research and thinking skills. According to N. G. Alekseeva, through reading books, a student not only gains knowledge, but also assimilates spiritual values, aesthetics, and moral norms.

Promoting a reading culture among students helps to prevent many harmful vices. I.S. Zbarsky noted that there are three important components in the formation of a reading culture in a person. [3]: 1) Cognitive component - characterized by the formation of spiritual consciousness, artistic erudition, and worldview in students. 2) Emotional component - determined by the formation of aesthetic feelings, a system of emotional values, and higher feelings in students. Behavioral component - students' skills in observing social norms of behavior, moral worldview are cultivated.

The following conclusions can be drawn regarding the issue of educating a culture of information acquisition in an information and library institution: The issue of educating a culture of information acquisition is a social, spiritual-enlightening, nationwide problem. This is not a

phenomenon limited to a certain period, but a spiritual need that a person learns throughout his life.

Reading culture is a person's positive attitude towards books, the need for reading, critical analytical thinking and the internal need for self-education. This culture plays a key role in the formation of human thinking, spiritual maturity and moral education.

Modern pedagogical and psychological research shows that students who have developed a positive attitude towards reading stand out from others in their professional preparation, communication culture and outlook on life.

South Korean professor Lee Seong-hyun's pedagogical research cites several experiences of teaching children to read. According to his research, it is difficult to form this competence in children if their parents are not readers.

Conclusion. Today, the issue of developing a reading culture among students is of urgent importance. Therefore, an effective methodology for developing a reading culture within the framework of pedagogy and psychology is a process that ensures not only the student's knowledge and skills, but also his personal, social and psychological development. Therefore, methodological approaches should be based on the individual characteristics of the student, active learning, a combination of communication and digital technologies. The formation and development of a reading culture in students is an important factor in their professional, moral and spiritual development as mature individuals.

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